

FEATURES OF DIET THERAPY FOR CHRONIC LIVER DISEASES

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In chronic liver diseases, nutritional status is often disturbed with the development of malnutrition of one degree or another. The use of nutritional support based on the nosological and syndromic approach makes it possible to create optimal conditions for the normalization of the function of the affected organ, increasing the effectiveness of other types of therapy and improving the prognosis of the disease.

The liver occupies a central place in the hepatobiliary system, participates in all metabolic processes. Almost half of the protein synthesized in the body is formed in the liver - these are structural proteins that provide reparative processes in tissues, as well as enzyme proteins, blood plasma proteins (albumins, globulins, fibrinogen, prothrombin) and protein-lipid complexes (lipoproteins, glycoproteins, bile lipid complexes and etc.). The liver also plays an important role in protein breakdown and amino acid conversion, in the processes of deamination and transamination.

The traditional approach to the diet therapy of viral hepatitis attaches great importance to therapeutic nutrition in these diseases. This approach was formed in the middle of the last century, and many domestic nutritionists and some gastroenterologists continue to adhere to it at the present time.

In infectious diseases, therapeutic nutrition helps to increase the body's defenses, restore damaged tissues, accelerate recovery, prevent the transition of the disease to a chronic form and the formation of complications. Therapeutic nutrition can increase the effectiveness of pharmacotherapy and reduce the likelihood of adverse effects on the body of a number of drugs.

The general characteristic of the therapeutic nutrition used was the physiologically normal content of proteins and carbohydrates with a slight restriction of fats (mainly

refractory). Foods rich in nitrogenous extractives, purines, cholesterol, oxalic acid, essential oils and fat oxidation products that occur during roasting were excluded.

Essential in achieving a therapeutic effect is a sufficient content of dietary fiber, which helps to accelerate the excretion of metabolic products and toxic agents from the body. These and other dietary requirements for diseases of the hepatobiliary system are met by the main version of the standard diet.

An important aspect of diet therapy for acute and chronic hepatitis has been and will remain the principle of compliance in the incoming food with the content of basic nutrients and energy.

Culinary processing of dishes in acute and chronic hepatitis includes boiling, steaming, baking and poaching. With these cooking methods, the formation of extractive, irritating substances is practically not observed.

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